

Annex to:

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Annex B – Tutorial for Data Provider user of the EFSA One Health WGS System for submitting Experimental, Typing and Epidemiological dataset using the WGS portal

1. Upload of Experimental data and generation of Typing data

1.1. Upload FASTQ from local computer

1.1.1. Single upload

This action is performed using a dedicated window in the EFSA One Health WGS System and it includes three steps.

Step 1 Experimental data

The user has two options to perform this action:

- Go to the home page by clicking on the EFSA logo at the top left and click on the “Upload your FASTQ now” button.
- Go to the Data Overview page, click on the “Upload” option on the bar menu and select “Single entry”.

The user inserts the Experimental dataset by compiling the required fields in the pop-up window (Figure 1). The user can access directly the required EFSA catalogues by clicking on the drop-list menu for each data element. The user selects the term name in the drop-list menu (the system will automatically store in the database the corresponding code).

Figure 1: Pop-up window uploading Experimental data of a single entry

The user selects the FASTQ file(s) to be uploaded by clicking “+ Upload file” and clicking “Next”. The system generates the MD5 checksum and validates the data. If the experiment is already assigned to

an Entry ID an error message will pop-up informing the user that it is not possible to upload the selected FASTQ files.

The system allows extensions *.fq.gz* or *.fastq.gz* and pairing information should be indicated as *_R1./_R2.* or *.R1./R2.* or *_1./_2.* or *_R1_L001./_R2_L001.* or *_R1.L001./_R2.L001.* or *.R1.L001./R2.L001.* or *_R1_001./_R2_001.* or *.R1_001./R2_001.* or *.R1.001./R2.001.* If the user attempts to upload FASTQ with a different format, an error message will pop-up.

Step 2 Epidemiological data

The user can select to upload Epidemiological data or not. In case the user intends to upload Epidemiological data, he or she clicks “yes” and inserts the required fields in the pop-up window (follow instruction showed in B.3, Figure 2) and then clicks “Next”. Otherwise, the user clicks “No” and “Next”.

Single upload, execute & release

1 Experimental data ———— 2 Epidemiological data ———— 3 Submit

Upload Fastq files and related experimental data.

Upload Epidata? Yes No

< Previous Next > Cancel * = mandatory field

Figure 2: Pop-up window for selecting if uploading or not Epidemiological data

Step 3 Submission

The user can select between two different types of processing: “Upload, execute and release (immediately)” or “Upload only” (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Pop-up window for selecting possible actions for single upload

By clicking “Upload, execute and release (immediately)”, after successful upload of the FASTQ the system automatically triggers the execution of the analytical pipeline and, in case of successful execution, immediately releases the entry to the EFSA One Health WGS database. If the user selects this option, he or she can also select the option to remove FASTQ after successful execution of the analytical pipeline by ticking the “Remove RawReads” box.

By clicking “Upload only” the FASTQ will be just uploaded in the system.

If the user wants to receive a notification upon completion of the upload, the box “Notification” should be ticked.

After selecting the right setting, the user clicks “Submit” and the upload starts. If the entry is created successfully, the user should see the following pop-up message (Figure 4):

Figure 4: Pop-up message informing user of the creation of the entry and the upload of the FASTQ files

A new entry has now been added to the grid in the “Data Overview” page and is marked as “Uploading”. The user can follow the uploading status by clicking the “loading” button in the top right part of the page.

During the upload it is important that the session of the application in the browser is not interrupted, closed or reloaded.

When the upload is finished, the entry status of the Experimental data table is marked as "Succeeded" and, if the user has selected to receive a notification, a notification will appear in the notification list, which can be opened by clicking on the bell symbol at the top right of the page.

1.1.2. Multiple upload

This action is performed using a dedicated window in the system.

The user goes to the Data Overview page, clicks on the "Upload" option on the bar menu and selects "Multiple entries" and the "Batch upload, execute & release" pop-up will be open (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Pop-up window for uploading data in batch mode

The user clicks on "Upload Directory" in the pop-up window and selects a directory in the local computer containing all FASTQ files to be uploaded. After selecting the folder, the user clicks on "Upload" in the pop-up and confirms the selection in the prompt that will appear by clicking "Upload".

The system allows extensions *.fq.gz* or *.fastq.gz* and pairing information should be indicated as *_R1./_R2.* or *.R1./R2.* or *_1./_2.* or *_R1_L001./_R2_L001.* or *_R1.L001./_R2.L001.* or *.R1.L001./R2.L001.* or *_R1_001./_R2_001.* or *.R1_001./R2_001.* or *.R1.001./R2.001.* If the user attempts to upload FASTQ with a different format, an error message will pop-up.

The upload of the files will start. As soon as a file is uploaded, it will appear in the pop-up window (Figure 6). The user can also follow the uploading status by clicking the "loading" button in the top right part of the page. **During the upload it is important that the session of the application in the browser is not interrupted, closed or reloaded.**

The files will be uploaded in a user-dedicated staging folder and they will be available until the user will either delete them or import them in the system. Other users even from the same organisation will not be able to access the staging folder.

Figure 6: Pop-up window for uploading data in batch mode showing FASTQ available in the user-dedicated staging folder

After all the selected files have been uploaded, the user goes back to the pop-up window and inspects the list of uploaded files. The user then clicks on "data batch file". This action results in the downloading of an excel file with a line corresponding to each Entry.

The user opens the file and inserts the Experimental dataset for all Entries by compiling the required fields in the "RawRead" sheet (Figure 7). The user can access directly the required EFSA catalogues by clicking on the arrow that appears at the right of a cell after selecting the cell. The user can also edit the pre-compiled fields, especially "Include" and "Processing Type". The user sets "Include" to "True" for the Entry to be imported. Under "Processing Type", the user chooses whether to "upload", "upload and execute", "upload, execute and clean" (this function will automatically delete the FASTQ files after the successful run of the pipeline) "upload, execute and release", or "upload, execute, release and clean" (this function will automatically delete the FASTQ files after the release). By choosing "Upload, execute and release" or "upload, execute, release and clean", after successful upload of the FASTQ the system automatically triggers the execution of the pipeline and in case of successful execution, immediately releases the entry to the EFSA One Health WGS database.

A	B	H	J	L	N	P	R
Info: Fill in this sheet to upload multiple RawReads							
Local RawReads ID	Include (choose false to exclude entry from upload)	Instrument Model	Isolate Species	Subtype	Processing Type	FastQ1 File Name	FastQ2 File Name
List1	FALSE				UploadExecuteRelease	List1_1.fastq.gz	List1_2.fastq.gz

Figure 7: Example of "RawRead" sheet

The user can select to upload Epidemiological data or not. In case the user intends to upload Epidemiological data, he or she sets the "Include epidemiological data" field to "True" in the "EpidemiologicalData" sheet (Figure 8) of the data batch file and inserts the required fields in the same sheet (following instruction showed in B.3).

A	B	C	H	I	K	M	N	O	P	Q	S	T	V	X	Z	A
Info: Fill in this sheet to upload multiple RawReads																
Local RawReads ID	Includes Epidemiological data	Existing sampling	Sampling Id	Sampling Country	Sampling Matrix	Sampling Matrix Free	Sampling	Sampling	Sampling	Programme Type	Programme Info	Sampler	Sampling Point	Sampling Area	Existing isolations	Isolate
List1	FALSE															

Figure 8: Example of "EpidemiologicalData" sheet

After filling the data batch file, the user saves it locally and goes back to the pop-up window in the system. The user clicks on "+ Upload file" next to "Data batch file" (Figure 5). The user selects the filled data batch file that was saved locally and uploads it to the window. The user then clicks on "Start".

The system generates the MD5 checksum and validates the data. After a check, another excel file will download automatically, named "BatchUpload_Results".

If there are errors, none of the files will be uploaded. The user is expected to inspect the file to see the nature of the errors, fix them following the indication printed in the file and reupload the excel data batch file. If the experiment is already assigned to an Entry ID an error message will inform the user that it is not possible to upload the selected FASTQ files.

If there are no errors, the Entries are created successfully, added to the grid in the "Data Overview" page and marked as "Uploading". When the upload is finished the entry status of the Experimental Data table is marked as "Succeeded".

1.2. Import FASTQ from ENA

1.2.1. Single ENA import

This action is performed using a dedicated window in the system and is composed by three steps.

Step 1 Experimental data

- Go to the home page by clicking on the EFSA logo at the top left and click on the "Upload your FASTQ now" button.
- Go to the Data Overview page, click on the "Upload" option on the bar menu and select "Single entry".

The user ticks the box "Indicate that you wish to import ENA data using the accession code" next to "ENA submission". Then, the user inserts the ENA accession number in the "ENA submission" field and clicks on "Next". If the FASTQ files are already assigned to an Entry ID an error message will pop-up informing the user that it is not possible to import the selected ENA accession.

Figure 9: Pop-up window for importing a single ENA accession

The system allows the import from ENA of sequences from *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes* or *Staphylococcus* spp. If the user attempts to upload FASTQ files assigned to a different species, an error message will pop-up.

Step 2 Epidemiological data

The user can select to upload Epidemiological data or not (Figure 2). In case the user intends to upload Epidemiological data, he or she clicks "yes" and inserts the required fields in the pop-up window (follow instruction showed in B.3), and then clicks "Next". Otherwise, the user clicks "No" and "Next".

Step 3 Submission

The user can select between two different types of processing: "Upload, execute and release (immediately)" or "Upload only" (Figure 3).

By clicking "Upload, execute and release (immediately)", after successful upload of the FASTQ the system automatically triggers the execution of the pipeline and, in case of successful execution, immediately releases the entry to the EFSA One Health WGS database. If the user selects this option, he or she can also select the option to remove FASTQ after successful execution of the analytical pipeline by ticking the "Remove RawReads" box.

By clicking "Upload only" the FASTQ will be just uploaded in the system.

If the user wants to receive a notification upon completion of the upload, the box "Notification" should be ticked.

After selecting the right setting, the user clicks "Submit" and the upload starts. If the entry is created successfully, the user should see the following pop-up message (Figure 4)

A new entry has now been added to the grid in the "Data Overview" page and is marked as "Uploading".

The user can follow the uploading status by clicking the "loading" button in the top right part of the page.

During the upload it is important that the session of the application in the browser is not interrupted, closed or reloaded.

When the upload is finished the entry status of the Experimental Data table is marked as "Succeeded" and, if the user has selected to receive a notification, a notification will appear in the notification list, which can be opened by clicking on the bell symbol at the top right of the page.

1.2.2. Multiple ENA import

This action is performed using a dedicated window in the system (Figure 10).

Before starting, the user uses a text editor to prepare a text file (.txt) with the list of accession numbers of the entries to import from ENA. The accession numbers should be separated by commas and with no spaces, e.g. SRR234789,ERR283947 .

The user goes to the Data Overview page, clicks on the "Upload" option on the bar menu and selects "Multiple ENA entries".

The user clicks on "Run accession file" in the pop-up window and selects the text file in the local computer containing the list of accession numbers of the entries to import from ENA. After selecting the file, the user clicks on "Open" in the pop-up.

Import ENA entries
✕

Use this tool to import multiple entries at once from the public ENA database. Follow these steps to perform the import.

Prepare a text file containing comma separated ENA run accession codes. Press the button below and navigate to the newly created file. The screen will display a summary of the chosen ENA run accession codes.

Example file: SRR234789,ERR283947

Run accession	Validity	Action
 No Data		

⬇️ Run accession file

In accordance with the Terms of Use
Validate and import
Cancel

Figure 10: Pop-up window for importing multiple ENA accessions

A row corresponding to each ENA accession number will appear in the window. The user clicks on "Validate and import". If no errors are detected, a pop-up message saying "Request to ENA created" will appear.

The new entries are added to the grid in the "Data Overview" page and are marked as "Uploading".

The user can follow the uploading status by clicking the "loading" button in the top right part of the page.

During the upload it is important that the session of the application in the browser is not interrupted, closed or reloaded.

When the upload is finished the entry status of the Experimental Data table is marked as "Succeeded".

1.3. Generation of Typing data: execute and stop analytical pipeline

This action is performed using a dedicated window in the system.

The user goes to the Data Overview page, selects one or more entries for which the analytical pipeline has not yet been executed (e.g. automatically after the upload), and clicks on "Execute".

The user chooses whether to "Execute and release (immediately)" or "Only execute". By clicking "Execute and release (immediately)", after successful execution of the pipeline, the system immediately releases the entry to the EFSA One Health WGS database. The user can also select the option to remove FASTQ after successful execution of the analytical pipeline by ticking the "Remove RawReads" box.

The user clicks "Start". The Analytical Pipeline Status in the Data overview table will first change to "Requested", then "Queued", then "Running" while the pipeline is running, and eventually "Succeeded" or "Failed" depending on the outcome of the run.

In case the user wants to stop the execution of the pipeline, he or she can select one or more entries that are being executed, click on "Stop", and then confirm by clicking "Stop" in the pop-up window.

The Analytical Pipeline Status in the Data overview table will change to "Cancelled".

1.4. Explore data and view Analytical Result

The user goes to the Data Overview page and visualises all available information on his or her entries in a grid. The grid includes the following tables which are displayed when sliding the bar rightwards:

- Monitoring

- Experimental data
- Last actions
- Validity status
- Epidemiological data
- Analytical pipeline results
- Analytical pipeline E. coli
- Analytical pipeline QC
- ENA data

Tables include several hidden and unhidden columns. The hidden columns can be visualised by clicking on the ">" sign next to the title of the table.

The grid is composed by pages of 20 rows. The user can move between pages by selecting the "< >" or "<< >>" signs in the bottom right of the page.

The user can explore the grid tables showed in the Data Overview page by filtering by selected values on specific columns, or by ticking the boxes at the bottom left "Show only released", "Show only uploaded not executed", "Show only executed not released", "Show public", or "Show private".

The user can select which columns he or she wants to visualise by pinning columns to the left or right of the table or ticking the boxes corresponding to each column.

The user can sort the entries by a column by clicking on the title of that column. An arrow pointing up or down will appear next to the title.

To view details on an entry, the user can click on the 'three-lines' next to the entry ID he or she would like to inspect. In the pop-up window, the user can click the "View" option of "Experimental data", "Epidemiological data" or "Analytical pipeline" (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Screenshot showing the possible row actions

The user would then be directed to the Detail Overview page. In the Detail Overview page, the user can click on the blue "+" sign for visualising the content of the tables. In case the analytical pipeline failed, the error log is available under "Analytical pipeline results".

DETAIL OVERVIEW EFSA-S-2022-000028 X

^ Latest release

Analytical pipeline	Epidemiological data	Valid from	Valid to	Isolate species
-	-	March 04, 2022 - 10:00	-	L. monocytogenes

^ Experimental data

Local raw reads ID	Status	Last modified on	Species	Validity
SRR1556296	Succeeded	18/01/2022 - 15:15	L. monocytogenes	Valid

^ Analytical pipeline results

^ Validity status

Pipeline run ID	Valid from	Valid to	Validity
2ca0d58c-35f7-4cea-9462-56c5314c4740	18/01/2022 - 22:56	04/03/2022 - 10:47	Invalid
EpiData version	00000000-0000-0000-0000-000000000000		
Pipeline run ID	Valid from	Valid to	Validity
2ca0d58c-35f7-4cea-9462-56c5314c4740	04/03/2022 - 11:00		Valid
EpiData version	00000000-0000-0000-0000-000000000000		

Figure 12: Screenshot showing the detail overview of a single entry

For auditing the actions performed on an entry, the user can select the row(s) of which he or she wants to visualise the audit trail and click on the red "+" sign next to the entry ID to unhide the corresponding rows. Each row shows an action performed on that specific Sequence submission.

1.5. Delete entries and FASTQ

The user can delete entries by selecting the row(s) corresponding to the entries, clicking on "Delete" in the toolbar, clicking on "Entry", and clicking on "Delete" in the pop-up window. This action is only possible for entries that have not been released to the EFSA One Health WGS database.

Alternatively, the user can delete only the FASTQ files associated with one or more entries by selecting the row(s) corresponding to the entries, clicking on "Delete" in the toolbar, clicking on "Fastq files", and clicking on "Delete" in the pop-up window. This action is always possible for all entries regardless of their release status.

2. Release of data to the EFSA One Health WGS database

To release data to the EFSA One Health WGS database, the user goes to the "Data Overview" page and select the row(s) of interest. For this action to be available, only entries with pipeline run status "Succeeded", which have not been released yet, can be selected. The user then clicks "Release" in the toolbar and "Start release" in the pop-up window.

The pipeline run status will change from "Succeeded" to "Released" and the entry/entries will be available for queries and generating trees.

In case the user later on decides to unrelease the entry, he or she goes to the "Data Overview" page, selects the row(s) of interest with pipeline run status "Released", and clicks on "Un-release" in the toolbar. The user clicks "End release" in the pop-up window.

The pipeline run status will change from "Released" to "Unreleased" and the entry/entries will not be available anymore for queries and generating trees, starting from the moment when the unrelease action was performed. Queries and trees generated during the validity period of the entry will remain valid.

3. Assign Epidemiological data to Entry ID (optional)

The user may assign epidemiological data to an entry at different stages:

- during upload or import from ENA (single entry), by selecting "Yes" in the Epidemiological data section of the pop-up window and inserting the required fields;
- during upload (multiple entries), by setting the "Include epidemiological data" field to "True" in the Epidemiological Data sheet of the data batch file and inserting the required fields;
- at any time after upload/import by clicking on "Edit" in the toolbar and selecting "Epidemiological data".

The mandatory fields are marked with a red asterisk (or are highlighted in yellow in the case of the multiple entries upload). The sample can be selected among already existing samples (for the same organisation) or creating a new sample. If an existing sample is selected, other fields will be pre-compiled except for the isolate.

For most fields (e.g. Programme type, Sampling point, Sampling country, Sampling matrix code), the user can choose from a defined list of elements that can be visualised by expanding the field clicking on the arrow pointing down. Alternatively, the user can start typing in the field and possible elements matching your text will appear. Other fields are free-text fields (e.g. Programme info, Sample local ID, Sampling matrix free text).

The user is required to select an isolate. In case isolations have already been associated to the selected sample, the user can select an existing isolation (e.g. in case of re-sequencing of an isolate). If the isolation is a new one, the user selects "New isolation" and inserts an Isolation Local ID (mandatory) and Isolation date (not mandatory).